

THE MIDNIGHT ROTATING TREE : COLLECTIVE GALLERY

A CATALOGUE OF TREES & CIRCLES

THE MIDNIGHT ROTATING TREE* is a research project that builds around practical seminars and their outcomes. It was designed to explore how we use visual rhetoric to express different forms of knowledge, in different contexts.

The first two seminars took place at the Faculty of Arts and Humanities of the University of Porto, in July and September 2024. These practice-based seminars involved the study and use of visual data and organisational archetypes - **circular and arboreal diagrams** - as tools with creative and pragmatic potential for learning and research.

The work developed by participants, members and speakers during the seminars was later curated for a virtual exhibition, *The Midnight Rotating Tree : Collective Gallery*, and a printed catalogue.

With **A CATALOGUE OF TREES AND CIRCLES**, we aim to showcase some of the ways in which participants experimented with using drawings and diagrams to communicate their feelings and their thoughts.

For more about the project, visit our website:
<https://ifilosofia.up.pt/projects/the-midnight-rotating-tree>

* The name of the project was inspired by the short tale "The Midnight Library", written by Matt Haig in 2020. It is affiliated to a larger project that investigates a diagrammatic book-game, published by João de Barros in 1540. Both authors use trees as metaphors for the complexity of human life, and circles as a means of "playing" with life.

Featured participants: Adelaide Morgado, Carla Santos Carvalho,
Celeste Pedro, DRP, Joana Nascimento, Manuel Ramos,
Pedro Simões, Sílvia Patrício, Sofia Santos and
Vanda Maldonado.

Thinking at the edge of a sleeping tree

corpo
 pele
 proteção
 casca
 nos
 nó
 feixe
 linha
 filamento
 ligação
 contínuo
 direção
 sentido do
 tempo

gnáca
 encait
 viver
 virtude
 meio
 natureza
 dia
 água
 pensa
 audência
 origem
 aiz
 meaa
 eu
 ore
 o

ignio

Drawing a tree (Punam) up side down to find a shape for research in art-education. 2024

Title

A Catalogue of Trees and Circles

Editor

Celeste Pedro
Instituto de Filosofia
Faculdade de Letras
Universidade do Porto

Design

Lara Mendes

Cover illustration

Silvia Patrício

Printed by

Casulo d'Imagens, Lda.

Copies

200

1st Edition

December 2024
Porto, Portugal

Doi: 10.5281/zenodo.14640391

THE MIDNIGHT ROTATING TREE : COLLECTIVE GALLERY | Ref.: IF.Proj.02.2024 Financed by the
Instituto de Filosofia with FCT funds: UIDB/00502/2020 and UIDP/00502/2020

Detail of plate: *Corporum Coelestium Magnitudines*
<https://paul.stanford.edu/mj82.441702>

